

Short communication

On the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Algeria

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Abstract. The presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) in Algeria is discussed. Recent records of the species in the country are reported.

Key words: Heteroptera, *Zelus renardii*, distribution, new record, invasive species, Algeria, Mediterranean Region, North Africa.

The invasive Nearctic assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) is widely distributed in the Mediterranean Region. Bella (2020), referring to Rattu & Dioli (2020), reported the species as present in Algeria, but Rattu & Dioli (2020) did not mention Algeria in their paper. Consequently, Baena & Santos (2021) doubted the presence of *Z. renardii* in Algeria and Kment & van der Heyden (2022) did not include the country in a map showing the distribution of the species in the Mediterranean Region.

Now, the presence of *Z. renardii* in Algeria can be reported, based on photographic records. On 12.VI.2023, Bernard Noguès photographed two nymphs of the species (Figs. 1 and 2) in Algiers, the capital of the country located at the Mediterranean coast. Both specimens were found on *Hibiscus* sp. (Malvaceae) in the botanical garden Jardin d'essai du Hamma. One nymph was preying.

These records are the first confirmed records of *Z. renardii* in Algeria and North Africa.

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Fig. 1. Nymph of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Algiers, Algeria (photo: Bernard Noguès).

Fig. 2. Nymph of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 with prey, Algiers, Algeria (photo: Bernard Noguès).

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